

Human Resources and Business Result: An Empirical Approach Based on RBV Theory

Authors : Xhevrie Mamaqi

Abstract : Organization capacity learning is a process referring to the sum total of individual and collective learning through training programs, experience and experimentation, among others. Today, in-business ongoing training is one of the most important strategies for human capital development and it is crucial to sustain and improve workers' knowledge and skills. Many organizations, firms and business are adopting a strategy of continuous learning, encouraging employees to learn new skills continually to be innovative and to try new processes and work in order to achieve a competitive advantage and superior business results. This paper uses the Resource Based View and Capacities (RBV) approach to construct a hypothetical relationships model between training and business results. The test of the model is applied on transversal data. A sample of 266 business of Spanish sector service has been selected. A Structural Equation Model (SEM) is used to estimate the relationship between ongoing training, represented by two latent dimension denominated Human and Social Capital resources and economic business results. The coefficients estimated have shown the efficient of some training aspects explaining the variation in business results.

Keywords : business results, human and social capital resources, training, RBV theory, SEM

Conference Title : ICAEBM 2014 : International Conference on Applied Economics, Business and Management

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : May 26-27, 2014